

SANDWICH STRUCTURES AT 300 M. WATER DEPTH. DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION ON THE DRAUGEN FIELD.

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ABSTRACT

In summer 1993 three subsea oil-wells in the North sea was protected with WPS (Wellhead Protection Structures) made of GRP (Glassfiber Reinforced Polyester) Sandwich. The WPS protect the subsea wells from overtrawling with fishing gear and from dropped objects. The development of the light weight protection structure started in 1986. The work was part of a contract for the Draugen subsea development which was performed on behalf of A/S Norske Shell. Maritime Seanor was awarded the EPC contract in April 1992, and all 3 structures was delivered on schedule one year later.

INTRODUCTION

From the early GRP Sandwich structure which was developed in co-operation with A/S Norske Shell to the present concept many turns on the design spiral have been made with regard to foundation method, operation, layout, installation and size. The sandwich concept has however remained unchanged with the foam core and the GRP skins on either side. The first concepts were structures based on much the same principle as for steel structure. The original thought was to give full access for a WROV (Work Remote Operated Vehisel) through permanent openings in the structure, and having a hatch on the top to give access to full intervention on the wellhead equipment without removing the protection structure.

This lead to a GRP sandwich structure with a geometry which was complex to fabricate in order to be overtrawlable, and the advantage or the material were not used to the full potential. Two years later a new idea was born and further development made.

CONCEPT DESCRIPTION

The protection structure for Draugen are designed using a totally different approach. To obtain overtrawlability with a geometrically simple and light structures was the aim from the start. This approach lead to a structure with the following main parts: a base frame which is a steel box girder and has a horse shoe shape, a GRP sandwich cage and a GRP sandwich Flowline Protector made of flat panels, and with few openings.

The overall size is 20 m long by 13 m wide and 8 m high, and the total weight is 68 tonnes. Due to the open horseshoe design of the bottom frame, the structure can be installed after the X-mas tree and the flowline/umbilical has been installed.

The structure has no physical contact with the X-mas tree after installation. Hence any loads from overtrawling will not be transferred into the well. Flowline/umbilical will enter through the open end of the horseshoe. Access for inspection ROV is through the access window in the structure. By entering through different windows all critical inspection tasks on the equipment can be performed. For heavy maintenance / work over operation or any other operation that require full access to the equipment, the GRP cage will be opened. The cage can open completely to either of three sides rotating around hinges on top of the base frame to give full access to the equipment. Opening of the cover is by WROV operation of six locking mechanisms, and using a wire from the surface for operation. The cover is nearly buoyant, so operation requires very low forces. This avoids problems with large masses and heavy impact during operation which have been a problem with steel hatches.

The structure has been designed completely overtrawlable with mudline penetrators in the corners to avoid snagging of the trawl gear underneath the bottom frame, and smooth flat panels in the Cage and Flowline Protector. All openings in the Cage have a size and location which prevents a trawl board from snagging. The corners of the Cage and Flowline Protector are rounded to further enhance the overtrawlability. The protection structure is secured to the seabed by four steel piles which are swaged after piling. The Flowline Protector guards the umbilical / flowline against trawlboard hooking and dropped objects in the critical free span area close to the well.

The GRP sandwich is completely maintenance free over the planned lifespan of the field, 20 years. The conditions at 280 m. waterdepth are perfect for this material with constant pressure and low temperature. The low weight of the structures give far better flexibility with regards to installation vessel than for heavier steel structures.

Figure 1. Wellhead Protection Structure

DESIGN REQUIREMENT

The design basis include a number of requirements, for this section only the unusual and unique requirements are listed below. The size and layout are directed by functional requirements:

- Size of X-mas three and clearance to this
- A shape capability of deflecting the trawl gear equipment
- ROV access both for a small inspection vehicle and a large working task vehicle

When the shape and functionality are decided the following load cases determine the cross section of the sandwich :

- Load from splash zone and waves during installation.
- Load from a passing trawlgear. Design load is 30 tonnes at two location at same time.
- Impact from trawlboard or dropped object : 10 kJ
- Water depth 300 meters
- Design life 20 years.

The highest utilization in the laminate was found to occur during installation of the cage (lift in wave zone). In this situation the maximum stress occur in the corner of the cage. The stress utilization during overtrawling is only 70%. In this case the global buckling dictate the maximum stress in the laminate. The Earthquake condition introduce stresses exceeding the design strength in local part of the structure. For this load condition the materialfactor is not taken into account because of the low probability of event, and the characteristic material properties, (laboratory values) can be used for acceptance criteria during design.

OVERTRAWLING TESTS

The WPS was tested for maximum load during overtrawling with fishing gear. For this purpose a 5 meter deep basin was used, a model in scale 1:10 was manufactured and fishing gear in same scale was used. Previous test with traditional protection structures end up with a characteristic load of 2 x 60 tonnes from the sweep line (wire) and 60 tonnes point load from snagging with the trawlboard.

In the case with the new Sandwich cage the maximum characteristic load was 2 x 11 tonnes from the sweep line and 12 tonnes point load when the trawlboard was towed over the WPS. This was the first structure ever in the North Sea that could prove a 100 % overtrawlable structure and get accept for a reduction in the characteristic design load. Again the Sandwich structure documented the bonus of going with this idea. Nevertheless, the offshore industry is rather conservative and it was agreed to design the WPS for 2 x 30 tonnes.

IMPACT TESTING AND PERFORMANCE

Maritime Seanor has also performed impact test on different types of panel to investigate the resistance to dropped objects. The tests have been performed using a free fall impact specimen, and the test panels submerged 1 m under water to better simulate actual conditions. Through this testing programme it has been verified that the GRP Sandwich used for Draugen can withstand more than 50 kJ impact load without penetration, which is five times higher than the specification required on the Draugen Field.

In general the test setup is an open steel frame which provide a simple support for the Sandwich panel along 4 sides. The free span of the test panel is 1 meter by 1 meter. The impact specimen of 1000 kg. was dropped from 5 meters, which represent 50 kJ energy. The nose of the impact

specimen was equipped with a half sphere with radius 100 mm. By variation of the drop height the impact energy can be altered from 1 kJ to 100 kJ. In addition to lower the test panel 1 m. down into the water, it is also important that the surrounding water have enough volume to simulate the real case. In our tests the distance to bottom and sides in the test basin was 5 meter. The oil companies (Norske Shell, Saga Petroleum, Norsk Hydro etc.) have accepted this test set up and acceptance criteria.

When study the sandwich panel after the impact test it was obvious that the shear capacity of the core, fracture elongation and bounding was significant for impact performance. Only 5 meter drop height present low speed impact and a quasi static load for a simplicity approach when discussing the fracture of the sandwich.

SELECTION OF MATERIALS

For the GRP laminate the Ahlström Combimat was used, which is a woven roving : 400 g. warp /400 g. weft + 300 g. CSM. In general 5 layers of this combimat was used, in some areas with higher load the number of combimat was increased to 10. In addition two layers with CSM (450 g.) on all surfaces, this to protect for slings, shackles and wires. Att last coating was added to minimize water ingress.

The polyester was Jotun Norpol 20M-80 which was quiet new that time. It was mainly developed for the Norwegian Marine to be used in high speed light crafts. The experience with this polyester is superb, friendly for hand lay-up and very low water absorption.

The core material was ordered from Airex which provide a copolymer PVC with high shear elongation before failure. Density just above 330 kg/m³ give structural properties which fulfil the requirement for long term strength. The compression load at 300 meter depth represent 2.85 N/mm², over 20 years this initiate creep in the core and has to be designed for.

MATERIAL FACTORS

A major concern for Maritime Seanor right from the start of this project has been to meet the documentation requirement for the offshore structures. This has traditionally been a weak point in GRP fabrication as very few rules and standards exist. To obtain a well documented quality product, Maritime Seanor has specified and procured the raw material for the GRP sandwich fabrication in close connection with the material suppliers. In addition very tight follow up and quality control during all parts of the fabrication is performed with strict procedures and requirements to documentation of every step of the process.

With respect to plastic composites there are no regulations issued specially for offshore oil and gas, neither are there any authorized design code or recommendations for plastic composites in general. There are regulations for specific applications such as pressure tanks and boats, but these are not very useful for the subsea protection structure. The theory for selection of material coefficients are therefore based on tentative recommendations for GRP structures by Norwegian Association of Civil Engineers. The theory and system for selection of material factor is the same as used in British Standard for design of pressure vessel.

Design strength $f_d = f \times (C_T \times C_1 \times C_M) / (3 \times U_1 \times U_2 \times U_3) = f / U_M$, where f = laboratory test value.

Table 2. Material Factors

		min.	max.	selected	
C_T	reduction factor due to temperature	0.8	1.0	1.0	low temperature
C_t	reduction factor due to long term loading	0.7	1.0	1.0	trawl load only
C_M	reduction factor due to environment	0.8	1.0	0.9	isofthalic/orto polyester in sea water at 5 deg.
U_1	coefficient of accuracy of analysis	1.0	1.2	1.0	high level of QC in design
U_2	coefficient of manufacture	1.0	1.8	1.2	high lev. of QC in manufac-turing
U_3	coefficient of consequence of failure	1.0	1.25	1.0	moderate consequence

Thus $U_M = 3 \times 1.2 / 0.9 = 4.0$ for ULS (Ultimat Load State)
 $U_M = 1.0$ for PLS (Progressive collaps Limit State)
 $U_M = 1.0$ for FLS (Fatigue Limite State)

Design Strength

Taking the material factor into account, the following design strength apply to the laminate:

$$\begin{aligned} fd_t &= 261 / 4.0 = 65.3 \text{ MPa} \\ fd_c &= 242 / 4.0 = 60.5 \text{ MPa} \\ vd_s &= 95 / 4.0 = 23.8 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

For core, which is manufactured under maximum control and traceability the material factor can be reduced to 2 and the following design strength apply :

$$\begin{aligned} fd_t &= 5.0 / 2.0 = 2.5 \text{ MPa} \\ fd_c &= 9.0 / 2.0 = 4.5 \text{ MPa} \\ vd_s &= 5.0 / 2.0 = 2.5 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

For certain details, as for instance hinge connections, consequence of failure would be critical and thus the materialfactor for this local areas was increased. If also the quality control of the manufacture was difficult to for such details the materialfactor end up with 5.8 .

INSTALLATION

During summer 1993 all facilities on the Draugen Field was installed. The 3 WPS was mobilized onto deck of the Semi-submersible Amethyst at 1 of June. The initial mobilization include lift on to deck all three structures, and an number of required spread for the operation onto the field. Approximately 400 tonnes was lifted onboard and seafastened during a couple of days.

In general the installation on the Draugen Field was characterized by an WROV (Work Remote Operated Vehicle) intensive operation and an increased requirement of accuracy and safety when installing equipment over existing wells. The 3 wells was exploration wells which was decided to be used also during production of oil. Any harm to one of the wells would influence on date of first oil and consequently the cash flow for the field.

The WPS was installed in 3 operations, starting with the steel base frame which was lowered down to 350 m. depth. Then two guidewires was established via the steel base and down to the x-mas tree. The guidewires was tensioned up to 5 tonnes and the base frame was lowered down along the guidewire and centred around the x-mas tree. The base frame was then secured with four piles.

Figure 2. Stack up of WPS

The GRP cage was then lifted of deck and lowered into sea with use of an installation frame. The cage was light and the shape induce wave forces onto the cage. In order to avoid snap in the lift wire the installation frame was equipped with several tonnes of weight. The loads during lowering trough the splash zone was govern load for the laminate on some areas on the cage. Guide wires was also used during finale lowering of the cage onto the base frame. When landed onto the base frame, the cage was secured to the base with latch/hinges on three sides. All three cages was left in closed position waiting for the tie-in and connection of the flowline. In order to reduce the load when lowering into the waves the roof on top of the cage was flipped over to allow water flow trough the cage. When the cover was installed the WROV closed the roof and locked it down to the cage.

After some weeks the flowline was installed and one Flowline Protector at the time was mobilized on deck of the monohull vessel : Seaway Condor. After opening the cage completely, the vessel finish the flowline tie-in and connection. The Flowline Protector was then lifted with help of an installation frame and lowered down to 250 m. depth. At this position two guidewires was established via the Flowline Protector down to the base frame. The guidewires was tensioned up and the Flowline Protector was further lowered along the guideline and entered into funnels on the base frame. Then the installation frame was released from the Flowline Protector and lifted up. The Flowline Protector was designed as an cantilever with full support from the base frame.

REDUCED COST AND WEIGHT

In parallel to the 3 WPS on Draugen Field, Maritime Seanor also delivered 6 steel structures for the Tordis Field. A simple compare between the two cases is shown in table 1. Cost and Weight.

Table 1. Cost and Weight

Field, Oil Company	Cost / unit	Weight / Unit
Draugen, Norske Shell	9 mill NOK (1.4 mill \$)	68 t
Tordis, Saga Petroleum	17 mill NOK (2.6 mill \$)	200 t

CONCLUSION

The WPS, which was a new concept and consider rather tricky to install, was installed in record time which has proven (and made stronger) the justification to go with this idea. After the flamboyant composite delivery to Norske Shell tonnes of composite subsea structures have been delivered to the offshore industry, Maritime Seanor has shown that this material are highly competitive to steel.

